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FORMATION OF A POLYFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE SYSTEM OF TRANSITION MECHANISMS OF UKRAINE TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Об'єктом дослідження є поліфункціональна структура системи механізмів переходу України до сталого розвитку. Використання концепції сталого розвитку суспільства, яка орієнтована на оптимальне задоволення потреб людей, забезпечує достатню якість життя, раціональне використання природних ресурсів і збереження довкілля, а основна увага акцентується на створенні певних передумов, сутність яких розкривається у даній роботі. Одними з не до кінця сформованих пріоритетних складових для формування умов сталого розвитку країни є:

- економічна (передбачає ефективне використання всіх видів ресурсів, орієнтованих на зниження або усунення тиску на природні екосистеми);
- екологічна (як шлях відновлення первинного стану природного середовища, збереження його на цьому рівні, реалізація заходів до максимально можливого поліпшення);
- соціальна (передбачає підвищення добробуту та якості життя людини, збереження її здоров'я).

В ході дослідження використовувались системно-інтегрований підхід управління механізмами сталого розвитку, які забезпечують соціально-економічний вектор становлення регіонів країни. Визначено, що структуру механізмів сталого розвитку формують державні та недержавні організаційні структури, які утворені на різних рівнях механізму та реалізують свої рішення через важелі впливу, що належать до їхніх повноважень, а саме через:

- нормативно-правове регулювання;
- податкову політику;
- бюджетно-фінансову політику;
- інформаційно-промоційне забезпечення тощо.

Завдяки зазначеним важелям вони можуть бути ефективними та сприяти досягненню основної мети організаційно-управлінського механізму у випадку чіткого розподілу повноважень на різних рівнях управління та з чітким контролем дотримання норм законодавства та визначених стратегічних цілей. Отримано висновок, що оптимальна поліфункціональна структура системи механізмів переходу України до сталого розвитку повинна поєднувати в собі структури всіх зазначених рівнів та механізмів, які б взаємодоповнювали один одного. А також спрямовували спільні зусилля на визначення та виконання стратегічних рішень.

Ключові слова: поліфункціональна структура, організаційно-управлінський механізм, сталий розвиток України, концепції сталого розвитку, системно-інтегрований підхід.

Received date: 20.11.2019

Accepted date: 18.12.2019

Published date: 28.02.2020

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1. Introduction

The organizational and managerial mechanism is the central component of the state mechanism for regulating sustainable development (SD). The main goal of introducing the idea of sustainable development of Ukraine should be the desire to create conditions for the balanced development of its territories, as well as maintaining people's health, improving social status, and economic growth. This forms a certain mechanism that must be used to implement the vector of sustainable development strategy. For this, it is customary to single out such areas of its development as: legal, organizational, financial, economic and innovative, social, environmental and information. And also the priority should be the formation of financial sources on the basis of public-private partnerships.

The main objective of such a mechanism should be to create favorable conditions for the sustainable development of the country, this determines the relevance and nature of the study. So, the optimal organizational structure of the sustainable development management of Ukraine should combine the structures of all these levels, which mutually reinforce each other, and direct joint efforts to determine and implement strategic decisions.

2. The object of research and its technological audit

The object of research is the multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms of transition of Ukraine to sustainable development.

Within the framework of the object, the part that determines the subject of the study, namely, its characteristic in the form of three components necessary for the formation of the conditions for sustainable development of the country, is highlighted: economic, environmental and social. Through these components, an organizational and management mechanism is being built, which is the central component of the state mechanism for regulating sustainable development. Indeed, it is precisely because of its leverage that the main managerial decisions that determine the level of development in the country as a whole and its individual regions are implemented. The formation of such a nationwide organizational mechanism for regulating sustainable development is possible only through the implementation of certain models, the efficiency of which is confirmed by European practice.

3. The aim and objectives of research

The aim of research is to form a multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms for the country's transition in the coordinates of sustainable development. To achieve the aim, it is customary to focus on three priority components (environmental, economic and social), which are integral parts of the concept of sustainable development of society, and for this it is necessary to identify and solve the following tasks:

1. To formulate the concept of sustainable development from the account of priority components.
2. To reveal the main directions of the sustainable development strategy.
3. To characterize the organizational and managerial mechanism of sustainable development.
4. To determine the priority model of the national organizational mechanism for regulating sustainable development.

The solution of these tasks will complement the theoretical basis, which is not enough to form a complete picture of the totality of all components, which, in turn, will form the multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms of Ukraine's transition to sustainable development.

4. Research of existing solutions of the problem

Research in the direction of structuring the system of mechanisms for transition to sustainable development has been studied by scientists around the world over the past decades. Since the pace of sustainable development in the world is ahead of this process in Ukraine, scientific superiority in research should be given to foreign scientists. So, in the XXI century, actively investigated the organizational, social and legal directions of sustainable development [1]. Later, other scientists joined this issue in their studies [2, 3]. Information and financial areas went to other scientists in [4, 5]. The concept of cooperation with the state and the business sector also intersected between them [6]. And almost everyone explored the economic and innovative areas and environmental areas. But sustainable development, the concept of which is the need to strike a balance between the satisfaction of modern human needs and protecting the interests of future generations, including their need for a safe and healthy environment, requires constant updating of knowledge, the

use of innovative technologies and economic innovations. Therefore, their adaptation to the model of Ukraine is only partially possible, it is necessary to listen to the opinion of modern scientists and their research [4, 5], which note the attraction of corporate resources to achieve sustainable development goals. Therefore, the opinions of Ukrainian scientists took into account both this experience and the modern realities of Ukraine. So, in [7, 8], based on the experience of foreign colleagues, they distinguish various structures of the system of mechanisms of Ukraine's transition to sustainable development. It is important to note that this industry constantly requires scientific intervention [9]. Other scientists identify the same areas without which this or that structure can't function [10, 11]. Separately, it should be noted the regional approach to the formation of sustainable economic development [12].

The result of the study of existing solutions to this problem is the integrative unity of socio-ecological and economic progress in the concept of sustainable development [13]. A generalization of existing structures will lead to a single multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms for Ukraine's transition to sustainable development [14, 15].

5. Methods of research

In the process of carrying out the research, general scientific and special research methods were used.

Among the special methods, it is possible to separately distinguish the method of statistical analysis, as well as a system-integrated approach. The first is used to study, group, compare, evaluate and interpret evidence on the nature and content of the concept of sustainable development, its direction, structure, mechanisms and concepts in general. The second allows to use the functional relationship between structures, determined by the quantitative effect of changes in the characteristics of one structure on changes in the characteristics of another.

General scientific methods of analysis were auxiliary used. These are the methods of generalization, comparison, integrated assessment and economic-statistical analysis, as well as the graphical method of presenting information.

6. Research results

Today, in the context of globalization of society, a definite concept of democracy has been formed, thanks to a socially oriented economy, it attached special importance to those mechanisms for introducing and encouraging sustainable development to create the prerequisites for Ukraine to become a member of the European Union [13].

The general idea of sustainable development is aimed at fairness and satisfaction of people's needs, the creation of conditions for a quality existence, the appropriate use of natural resources, and a responsible attitude to the environment. These factors only pay special attention to systems which functions should help the development of society (Table 1).

For the first time, the term «sustainable development» was officially adopted at the UN World Conference on Environment and Development, which was held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992. 27 principles were also identified, the desire to fulfill which is an indispensable institution for the movement of society towards sustainable development.

The «Program of Action» was adopted as a basis, which included the following decisions [2, 3]:

- issue of maintaining health, mental development and ensuring a healthy lifestyle;
- satisfaction of the material needs of society in modern conditions of the formation of an innovative economy;
- rational nature management, protection of non-renewable natural resources, protection of wildlife, the formation of a knowledge base on natural resource management;
- development of principles for the formation of a social market economy, an open economic system, mutually beneficial trade;
- creation of national systems, Internet resources on environmental issues, deployment of an agreed system of resource cadastres, pollutant release and transfer registers;
- social activity, citizen participation in the adoption and implementation of the environmental and economic development of the state.

Table 1

Key systems for sustainable development of society

System	Operating principle
Domineering	It has an adaptive nature, therefore it can easily adapt, self-correct and self-improve
Economic	Able to create conditions for innovative production, use scientific and technical progress (scientific and technological progress) and ensures the preservation or maintenance of the natural (ecological) system in a qualitative state throughout the whole time
Political	Creates conditions for participation of the general public in the adoption of most management decisions
Technological	It stimulates on an ongoing basis innovative developments, and is also engaged in the search for new effective and optimal solutions
Social	Relieves stress that may arise in the process of economic development of the country
International	Provides mutually beneficial development of trade, financial and political relations

Note: developed on the basis of data [13–15]

After that, the principles of sustainable development were combined into a concept, which was approved at a subsequent Rio+5 conference in 1997. Five years later, it was improved at the World Summit on Sustainable Development in 2002, in Johannesburg. After that, the concept began to be introduced into world practice. So, the main tasks in the production of the concept in Ukraine were: creating conditions between the balanced development of the regions and maintaining the health of the people living in them.

Based on the accumulated European experience, to formulate the concept of sustainable development of the country, it is necessary to focus on the implementation of such priority components (Fig. 1), such as:

- economics – from the concept of the concept of sustainable development provides for the rational and efficient use of natural resources, focused on the creation of an effective system of environmental protection;
- society – changes in social relations, which provide for social justice and integration processes;

- ecology – ensuring the integrity of biological and physical natural systems. Degradation of natural resources, environmental pollution and loss of biological diversity reduce the ability of ecological systems to self-repair.

The implementation of the country's sustainable development strategy requires the use of such a mechanism, which would be based on the internal and external economic priorities of the country and its regions. This is due to the fact that the main driving force of the modern state is its regions, and the synergistic effect of their development is to give the opportunity for socio-economic progress in entrepreneurship and in society.

For a multifunctional structure, it is customary to distinguish such systems of mechanisms for sustainable development strategies: organizational, financial, legal, social, informational, economic-innovative and environmental (Fig. 2).

Regulatory support for the formation of regional development planning in Ukraine:

- Constitution of Ukraine (Revision of 01.01.2020) is responsible for the legality of the whole process;
- Laws of Ukraine «On the Basics of State Regional Policy» dated 05.02.2015 No. 156, «On Local Self-Government in Ukraine» dated 21.05.1997 No. 280/97-BP, «On Local State Administrations» dated 09.04.1999 No. 586-XIV and «On state forecasting and development of programs for the economic and social development of Ukraine» dated 23.03.2000 No. 1602 III;
- Decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine «On approving the Procedure for developing the State Strategy for Regional Development of Ukraine and an action plan for its implementation, as well as monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the implementation of these Strategies and Action Plans» dated 11.11.2015 No. 931 and «On approving the Procedure for developing regional strategies development and action plans for their implementation, as well as monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the implementation of these regional strategies and action plans» from 11.11.2015 No. 932;
- Orders and Concepts of the state regional policy of the Ministry of Regional Development «On approval of the Methodological recommendations for the formation and implementation of forecast and program documents of the socio-economic development of the united territorial community» dated 30.03. 2016 No. 75 and «On approval of the Methodology for the development, monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the implementation of regional strategies development and action plans for their implementation» dated 31.03.2016 No. 79;

- other relevant acts of the President of Ukraine and normative acts of central, local executive authorities and local self-government of the respective region.

Regional development strategies are always directly related to such important processes as creating market relations, building new forms of ownership, continuous social development, the ecological condition of the region, population, migration, demography of the region and other processes [8].

Sustainable development of the economy of any country becomes possible only thanks to its innovative orientation – this is when both the specific features of the region and the mentality of its population are taken into account.

Fig. 1. The relationship of components in the concept of sustainable development

Fig. 2. The structure of the system of mechanisms for sustainable development

The sustainable development strategy is becoming the main factor that can effectively solve the economic, social and environmental problems of society and that is why the economic and innovation mechanism requires the use of a certain sequence of measures that will positively contribute to overcoming problems. And also guide the development of territories along the path of the following production processes, namely:

- innovation and investment process;
- use of high technology;
- saving of natural resources;
- functioning environmental component that positively affects the environment;
- organization of industrial safety.

The mechanism of sustainable development of Ukraine and its regions, which has an organizational direction, is based on the interest of territorial bodies and communities in the economic effect obtained from the work of most enterprises in the region (small, medium-sized businesses, as well as large enterprises). The combined efforts of enterprises will give a sufficient synergistic effect from the complexity of development. The aforementioned software implementation strategies should include:

- conceptual system for managing the development of a strategic direction;
- formation of an organizational structure, or a state body in order to implement a strategy, the essence of

which is to ensure joint actions of various levels of government in private and public organizations;

- form of control should ensure the implementation of the strategy by the private and public sectors.

Therefore, the primary condition for effective public administration is the optimal division of powers between the center and local governments.

An important aspect of the financial mechanism is the improvement of financial and budgetary relations between the center and the development of criteria and mechanisms for providing state support, the implementation of tasks and priority areas of the strategy to be financed from the state and local budgets, as well as other sources. During the financing of activities to implement the sustainable development strategy, all contractors must ensure that the planned tasks are met with maximum effectiveness and efficiency in their use.

The main priority should be the formation of financial sources through the use of public-private partnerships between the state and the private industrial, industrial and commercial complex.

State financial support for regional development is considered as simultaneous financing from state and local budgets. At the same time, the amount of funds from local budgets does not decrease in the case of financing the state-determined priorities in regional development. The share of local budgets in the implementation of the strategy is determined taking into account the level of socio-economic development of the region.

The social mechanism should contribute to creating conditions for improving the level and quality of life of the population by introducing social standards, forming an optimal network of social infrastructure institutions, directing investments in their further development and improving the quality of services. The indicators of the social orientation of development should be considered the dynamics of the real level of consumption of social benefits, fertility and mortality, physical and spiritual health of the population, life expectancy, etc. The social orientation of regional development should be evaluated and ensured taking into account the ideas of sustainability and balance.

The organizational and managerial mechanism is the main component of the state mechanism for regulating sustainable development, because it is through its levers of influence that the main managerial decisions find their place, which determine the level of development in the country in general and in its individual territories.

The organizational and managerial mechanism of sustainable development is formed by state and non-state organizational structures formed at different levels of the mechanism and implement their decisions through levers of influence related to their powers, namely because of:

- legal regulation;
- tax policy;
- fiscal policy;
- promotional information and the like.

These levers can be effective and contribute to the achievement of the main goal of the organizational and managerial mechanism in the case of a clear distribution of powers at different levels of management and with clear control of compliance with legal norms and certain strategic goals.

An effective organizational and managerial mechanism should act on the principles of transparency, efficiency, cost-effectiveness, efficiency and actively cooperate with other, including non-state, organizations that are interested in the

socio-ecological and economic development of the country. The main objective of such a mechanism should be to create favorable conditions for the sustainable development of the country. Current conditions for the development of global economic globalization require special approaches to the construction of an organizational and managerial mechanism, which should take into account the regional, national, cross-border, European integration and world level.

The optimal organizational multifunctional management structure for sustainable development of Ukraine should combine the structures of all these levels, which are mutually reinforcing, and direct joint efforts to determine and implement strategic decisions.

The organizational and managerial mechanism at the national and regional levels is the most interconnected and requires a clear distribution of powers in order to ensure the effective implementation of the state policy of regulating socio-environmental and economic components. When building a nationwide organizational mechanism for regulating sustainable development, the following models are possible:

1. The lack of a central state regulatory authority, all issues are resolved locally on the principles of market self-regulation. This model is used in countries where sustainable development does not play a big role for the national economy, or vice versa – the country has reached its highest development and does not require government intervention. An example of a country uses this model – the United States.

2. The presence of the state central regulatory authority for the sustainable development of the country and its territories. This may be a ministry that exercises control over the activities of subjects of socio-ecological-economic activity of the country. Such a model requires significant financial investments in the development of economic, social and environmental infrastructure.

3. The so-called European model, which provides for the functioning of a specialized structure for sustainable development as part of a diversified ministry. This model is used by most European countries.

When choosing one of these models, an important clear distribution of functional powers between central and local regulatory authorities. Given the European orientation of the country, a possible solution would be to use the third model, because the second requires significant financial investments, which today Ukraine can attract only through investment injections.

7. SWOT analysis of research results

Strengths. A stable and optimal multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms for Ukraine's transition to sustainable development will be able to combine structures of all levels and mechanisms, namely: legal, organizational, financial, economic and innovative, social, environmental and information. As well as the formation of financial sources based on public-private partnerships. The interaction of these mechanisms forms the definition and implementation of strategic decisions. Unlike other similar models, this one ensures the effective implementation of the state policy of regulating socio-ecological-economic components. And for sustainable development, they are priority.

Weaknesses. It is impossible to point out all the shortcomings of a system that has not yet fully worked out. However, it can be noted that the lack of a central state

authority for monitoring the activities of the subjects of socio-ecological-economic activity of the country and the regulation of sustainable development slows down the entire mechanism of transition to it. The regions of the country are independently trying to achieve their goals, the lack of funding does not allow them to be realized.

Opportunities. With systematic government investment in sustainable development programs, there is a chance to accelerate the country's exit on the path of sustainable development. The model is formed, there are successful examples of neighboring countries. A possible solution – if underfunding sustainable development programs, choose one or two areas of development (for example, socio-economic), but this will greatly slow down the entire transition process.

Threats. The topic of research on sustainable development is wide and important, therefore, it attracts the attention of many scientists. Theoretical values obtained today – tomorrow may no longer be relevant. Another threat is a small percentage of truly new developments, and the fact that European scientists have spent many decades studying and improving the concept of sustainable development, so new ideas are often updating obsolete developments, or upgrading the mechanism. But using precisely the multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms will help to occupy the right vector of Ukraine's transition to sustainable development.

8. Conclusions

1. The study shows the need to strike a balance between meeting the modern needs of humanity and protecting the interests of future generations, including their need for a safe and healthy environment. This requires constant updating of knowledge, the use of innovative technologies and economic innovations. The relationship of the components in the concept of sustainable development is disclosed and built.

2. Directions, or mechanisms, which are usually allocated for the formation of the general mechanism of the strategy for sustainable development of the region, are generalized to legal, organizational, financial, economic and innovative, social, environmental and information. For each of them, characteristics are given that generalize their structure.

3. The work indicates that the structure of mechanisms for sustainable development is formed by state and non-state organizational structures formed at different levels of the mechanism and implement their decisions through levers of influence related to their powers, namely because of:

- legal regulation;
- tax policy;
- fiscal policy;
- promotional information and the like.

Thanks to these levers, they can be effective and contribute to the achievement of the main goal of the organizational and managerial mechanism in the case of a clear distribution of powers at different levels of management and with a clear control of compliance with legal norms and certain strategic goals.

4. Three models of building a nationwide organizational mechanism for regulating sustainable development are identified. The first is based on the principles of market self-regulation, the second on the construction of the state central regulatory authority, the third European model. For Ukraine, the pro-European development course is optimal, that is, the European model is most suitable.

The optimal multifunctional structure of the system of mechanisms for Ukraine's transition to sustainable development should combine the structures of all these levels and mechanisms that would mutually support each other and direct joint efforts to determine and implement strategic decisions.

Acknowledgements

This work continues the research of Doctor of Economics, Professor S. Kharichkov.

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